

Number of States Derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Versus $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained by traditional argument (found in textbooks and also (1)) which considers the counting of the number of states with energy less than a value E , $W(E)$. Then, $d/de W(E-e)$ is the number of states with energy e for $e \ll E$. In (1), temperature is then defined as: $E = 3N/2 T$ (for three dimensions). In (1) it is also assumed that one has a quantum noninteracting gas in a square well potential with stochasticity and T presumably at the walls.

An alternative approach to find the MB distribution is to use reaction balance: $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$, for $p(e)$ unnormalized. This approach also gives rise to the maximization of Shannon's entropy (as a math function) subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = Eave$. (An independent derivation of the MaxEnt approach follows from considering \ln of the number of arrangements, $N!/ \prod_i n(i)!$ subject to the above constraint as long as one uses Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$).

We try to show that the counting of states approach of (1) is equivalent to the reaction balance method $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$.

Counting of States Method

In (1), it is argued that one has a quantum gas (presumably in an infinite well potential, i.e. a Fermi gas) that is non-interacting. It is, however, interacting with the walls which are linked with a temperature T and so there is stochasticity in the problem introduced by the walls.

The key approach to the argument of (1) is to find the number of states $W(E)$ with energy E or less. This is linked to geometry and we give the result of (1) as:

$W(E)$ proportional to E power $3N/2$ ((1)) where N is the number of particles

Then, (1) considers the case of a single particle with energy e and $N-1$ particles with energy $E-e$. To find the number of states, one takes d/de of ((1)), so:

Number of states for $N-1$ particles with energy $E-e$ is proportional to $(E-e)$ power $3N/2$ ((2))

because $3N/2 \text{ approx} = 3N/2-1$.

Number of states for 1 particle with energy e is proportional to e power $1/2$ ((3))

This leads to:

Probability(e) $de = C(T) (E-e)$ power $3N/2$ e power $.5$ $de =$

$C(T) \sqrt{e} de \exp(- e/E (3N/2))$ ((4))

In (1), T is defined through: $E = 3N/2 T$ so $P(e)de = C(T) \sqrt{e} de \exp(-e/T)$ ((5))

We wish to show that the above approach is equivalent to reaction balance, i.e. $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for p unnormalized and $e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l$.

Equivalence of the Counting of States Approach with Reaction Balance

We note that in the above calculation:

$$W(E-e, N-1) \approx W(E-e, N) \quad ((6))$$

Thus, we suggest that one may consider two particles whose energy adds to e, i.e. $(e-e_2)$ and e_2 . We generalize ((6)) to:

$$W(E-e, N-2) = W(E-e, N) \quad ((7))$$

From the point of view of $W(E-e)$ and its d/de derivative, one only considers a loss of energy e from E and does not worry if this is due to the removal of one or two particles.

There is, however, an effect due to the two particles because instead of:

$$d/de W(e, N-1) \text{ one has } d/de W(e) \text{ at } e_2 \text{ and } d/de W(E-e) \text{ at } e=e_2 \quad ((8))$$

We note that e_2 may be considered to be a constant. ((4)) then becomes:

$$P(e)de = \text{Constant} * de * (E-e)^{\text{power } 3N/2} (e-e_2)^{\text{power } .5}$$

Usually e runs from 0 to infinite, but if e represents two particles and one must have energy e_2 , then e runs from e_2 to infinite. One may change variables:

$$y = e - e_2 \quad (E - e)^{\text{power } 3N/2} \approx \exp(-e/T) \quad \text{and } dy = de \text{ so that one has:}$$

$$P(y)dy = \text{constant}^2 * dy \exp(-y/T) y^{\text{power } .5}$$

where y is integrated from 0 to infinite.

The probability itself is $\exp(-e/T)$ with $y^{\text{power } .5}$ being considered as part of the measure.

$$\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-(e_1+e_2)/T) \quad ((9))$$

We argue that the counting of states approach is equivalent to reaction balance. If one only thinks in terms of $d/de(E-e)^{\text{power } 3N/2}$, this conclusion arises immediately, but in the counting

of states approach, one must also consider the measure $\sqrt{e}de$ from $d/de (e \text{ power } 3/2) de$. If there are two particles, one with e_1 , one must ensure that the measure does not change and the change of variable to $y=e-e_1$ seems to indicate that the measure is not changed.

We argue that the counting of states approach is identical to reaction balance (if one assigns $\sqrt{e}de$ as a measure which does not affect an elastic collision) and that one may consider physical elastic 2-body scattering instead of a non-interacting quantum gas in an infinite potential as another physical example leading to the Maxwell-Boltzmann result. In other words, it does not seem that one must start with a quantum mechanical picture as (1) does. The key idea is that if one deals with a distribution of energy e . $W-e$ for large N can occur for e being assigned to one particle or two and the system is not sensitive enough to distinguish as N is very large.

Physical Interpretation of $\sqrt{e} de$

In (1), $P(e) de$ is proportional to $d/de (E-e) \text{ power } 3N/2 d/de (e) \text{ power } 3/2$. $p(e)$ includes both the single particle's possible states and that of the remaining gas. In a two body collision, in which one is only interested in the energy of a particle (for conservation of energy), one considers the particle as only having a single state e , (as one does not focus on momentum). Then $(E-e) \text{ power } 3N/2$ is the key piece of the probability associated with reaction balance $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l$ and $\sqrt{e} de$ is simply a counting measure for the number of momentum orientations. In particular, for $e = \text{kinetic energy} = pp^2/2m$, $de = p dp/m$. If one wishes to count all possible momentum states:

$$Pp dp 4\pi \rightarrow \text{proportional to} \rightarrow e de / \sqrt{e} = \sqrt{e} de \quad ((10))$$

This number of momentum states, however, is not seen as affecting a 2-body elastic collision as one is only interested in having e_i and e_j collide to produce e_k, e_l with $e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l$.

In (1), it is argued that one has a non-interacting quantum gas, but the gas particles must interact, otherwise there is no stochasticity. They interact with the walls, which means that one may consider $p(e_i)$ in the wall and $p(e_j)$ in the gas, and $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ should have physical meaning. The question is then whether \sqrt{e} from the calculation of (1), i.e. $d/de (e) \text{ power } 3/2$ affects an elastic collision. We argue that it does not and that one should only consider $(E-e) \text{ power } 3N/2$ as the probability describing a collision.

Conclusion

In (1), a counting of states approach is used to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $p(e) = C(T) \exp(-e/T)$. A quantum noninteracting gas in an infinite potential well is considered (with T related stochasticity given by the walls) and T formally defined as: $E = 3/2 N T$, for N particles. The key idea of (1) is that $W(E) = \text{number of states of } N \text{ particles with energy } \leq E$ is proportional to $(E-e) \text{ power } 3N/2$. The calculation of $P(e)de = de \text{ constant } d/de W(E-e, N) d/de W(e, N=1)$ which yields $P(e)de = de \text{ constant } \sqrt{e} \exp(-e/T)$ with $E=3N/2 T$ (as a definition of T). (Note: This is a 3-dimensional calculation.)

We argue that $\exp(-e/T)$ follows from $d/de (E-e)$ power $3N/2$ and that this term does not distinguish between one or two particles obtaining the energy e , because N is extremely large. $\exp(-e/T)$ is essentially the unnormalized Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, and so $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-(e_1+e_2)/T)$, i.e. $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l$. This may be physically applied to a non-quantum gas with 2-body elastic collisions. In other words, $\sqrt{e}de$ is a measure which does not affect the 2-body elastic collision analysis. One must, however, show that for e given to two particles, with one having energy e_2 (a fixed number), that the measure $\sqrt{e} de$ is not changed using the approach of (1). We try to do that in the above note..

References

1. Condon, E.U. A Simple Derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Law , Physical Review Volume 54, Dec. 1, 1938) <https://www.niser.ac.in/~bedanga/P101/PhysRev.54.937.pdf>